

PREVENTIVE PROTECTION OF THE INDIVIDUAL FROM CRIME

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7273209>

Annotation: Human rights need to be protected and protected by the state. Not the last place in ensuring state protection and protection of human rights is occupied by the prevention of offenses. In this regard, an important task of the state, represented by authorized bodies, is to establish the legal and organizational foundations of the crime prevention system, the general rules for its functioning, the basic principles and directions. An analysis of the current legislation indicates that the legal framework that ensures the protection of human rights, society and the state from unlawful encroachments, lags behind the needs of reality and law enforcement practice.

Key words: human rights, guarantees of citizens' rights, state, principle of humanism, preventive protection, law.

Preventive protection of the individual from crime is focused on the interests of society and the state and is integrated into the system of sociology and law. This doctrine proceeds from the fact that this protection is based on compliance with the requirements of the state and society, which guarantee the protection of the individual and ensure his safety. At the same time, society and the state, as it were, cede their rights and privileges to a person who is protected on their own behalf, demonstrating not their own priority, but the priority of the individual, person and citizen. In such a situation, the state and society do not lose, but gain, show humanism, democracy and a kind of nobility.

Society and the state will not be able to protect the individual from criminal encroachments without providing effective prevention of crimes by those who are capable of committing them. Realizing the principle of humanism, preventive protection, focused on ensuring the safety of members of society, is not against those who have already committed crimes (they are punished by the state), but for those who can still be saved from slipping into a criminal path. By preventing crimes, help is provided to those who might commit them, while at the same time the threat is averted from those against whom they could be committed. Crime always precedes punishment, and warning precedes crime. Indeed, a wise legislator would rather prevent a crime than be compelled to punish for it. It is important, of course, to identify the offender, to solve the crime, to ensure the

inevitability of punishment, but the most important thing is to prevent a crime, to protect a person from criminal encroachment. [1]. A special role in this belongs to preventive protection. It uses all social levers and the force of law to establish reliable barriers to crime. At the same time, preventive protection acts as a special form of social and legal regulation, and ensuring the security of the individual is manifested as a reaction of the state and society to crimes.

Preventive protection of the individual from criminal encroachments concerns all social aspects of criminological significance. It is integrated into the system of criminology, hence sociology and law. This doctrine proceeds from the fact that the protection of the individual is based on compliance with the requirements of society and on the provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens, protect human life and health, property, etc. Law and society protect the individual. Focusing precisely on the prevention of crimes, preventive protection brings to the fore the person who can commit a criminally punishable act and who can become its victim. At the same time, this protection establishes a bridge between general preventive measures addressed to the population as a whole and individual preventive measures [2]. This situation carries elements of the consistent development of social prevention, which includes legal means.

The system of protecting the individual from criminal encroachments, where constitutional protection occupies a central place, includes the following areas.

The first is the social protection of the individual. Here, all social institutions should be involved, the functional rights and duties of which are related to ensuring the safety of people from criminal encroachments.

The second is the economic protection of the individual. This concerns financial and economic issues, infringement of the relevant rights of citizens by actions of a criminal nature. Special here is the protection of people from the influence of the shadow economy.

The third is the legal protection of the individual, which includes prosecutorial supervision, judicial protection, etc. This refers to the protection of a person from crimes by legal means, the creation of conditions for the corresponding safety of people. This may include rule-making activities, information and legal support for activities to ensure this security, building a legal foundation for protecting a person, his rights and freedoms, legal control, creating more advanced legal mechanisms for protecting citizens from crime, generalizing and disseminating existing best practices, etc. Of particular note are the areas of activity of the prosecutor's office and the courts, the Ministry of Internal Affairs

and the State Security Service, the justice authorities, the tax inspectorate and the customs service, notary services, etc. The advocacy plays a huge role in this. As already noted, preventive protection against crime cannot be separated from ensuring public safety and strengthening the rule of law. Although not unambiguous concepts "appear" here, their unity is obvious. The protection of the individual and society from crime can be defined as a system of social relations determined by the needs of the development of a democratic state, the formation and improvement of which contributes to the tranquility of citizens, the consistency and rhythm of people's lives, the provision of personal and property inviolability, honor in mutual communication. and dignity, favorable conditions for the exercise by each person of his rights and freedoms. The object of preventive protection, closely related to ensuring public safety and strengthening the rule of law, is the life and health of a person, his peace of mind, rights and freedoms, property [3]. In addition, there is a strong link between crime prevention and law enforcement [4]. This refers to comprehensive prevention: social and moral, legal, general prevention and special (private) warning, which relates to the field of criminal law prevention, general and individual prevention of both criminal and victim behavior, and by branches of knowledge – administrative-legal, criminal procedure, forensic, penitentiary, operational-search, etc. It follows that preventive protection protects all social and personal-human values from criminal encroachments. In this regard, it is permissible to talk about the protective function of preventive protection, which is closely related to the protection of citizens from violations of the rule of law. In general, we are talking about ensuring the safety of citizens.

Protecting a person from hooliganism involves a wide range of social, legal, economic and other measures [5]. The question of ensuring public order also belongs to this complex. As practice shows, complex preventive measures included in the system of ensuring public order contribute to the successful implementation of the protection of the individual from hooliganism. All these activities are intertwined, providing public protection of order from gross violations, which is associated with a clear disrespect for society, and protection of the individual from violence used in hooliganism. There is also a connection with the rule of law, which integrates social (legal) relations based on the simplest rules of conduct: behave as the law requires. [6]. Such rules are based on social norms of morality, in which the state, society and citizens are interested, and without which social life is unthinkable. These rules fix the elementary conditions of human communication, which prevent crimes,

protecting the individual and society from criminal encroachments. According to such rules and in accordance with them, preventive protection of a person should be carried out. However, to increase the effectiveness of such protection, the prevention of criminal behavior is also needed, as well as the prevention of victim behavior. These are the main activities aimed at ensuring the protection of public safety and human protection.

The protection of public order and the protection of the individual are ensured by the normal functioning of all components of the "preventive complex". This is a kind of preventive system.

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